

D1.5.

Report containing tools

WP1 – Historical and comparative analysis

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822337.

**Populism and
Civic Engagement**

Authors	Dimitris Skleparis (DEMSOC, Newcastle University)
The accompanying Excel file has benefitted from comments by:	Takis S. Pappas (HU) Marco Fölsch (PLUS) Ruzha Smilova (CLS) Daniel Smilov (CLS)
Due date	April 30, 2021
Delivery date	2021
Type	Research Results
Dissemination level	Report, Public
Keywords	Populism, Nativism, Europe, Liberalism, Democracy

This accompanying document aims at explaining the contents of **‘D1.5 - Report containing tools’ Excel file** and includes some useful user guidelines. It should be noted that the Excel file in reference is a ‘beta’ version which was last updated on 15 April 2021. The data presented in the Excel file follow the typology developed in **D1.3** and presented in an interactive infographic included in **D1.4**. Users may find useful complementary contextual information for each of the 18 selected parties/case studies in **D1.1** and **D1.2**.

The Excel file is available on the PaCE website at the following link: <https://popandce.eu/2021/04/30/d1-5-report-containing-tools-excel-file/>

The Excel file consists of 21 spreadsheets, including a *Table of Contents* which provides users with shortcuts to each spreadsheet and lists the sources which were used in building this dataset.

Spreadsheet titled *Parties Master* includes 10 variables which provide users with some basic information about the 18 selected parties/case studies. More specifically:

- **‘Country’**: the country in which the party in hand emerged.
- **‘Party Name’**: the initials or short name of the party.
- **‘Full Party Name’**: the full name of the party in its original form and English translation.
- **‘Year Founded’**: the year the party was founded. NB. This might differ from the year that an entity was registered as a political party.
- **‘Party Type’**: the type of each party based on the typology developed in **D1.3** and presented in an interactive infographic included in **D1.4**. By clicking on the arrow next to the variable title users can select and compare different party types.
- **‘Political Position’**: the ideological positioning of the party (left-right).
- **‘Predecessor’s Name’**: the name (in English) and initials of the party that preceded the party in hand.
- **‘Total Number of Party Splits’**: the number of direct splinter parties from the party in hand. When users hover over cells that include a red earmark , they can see the name(s) of the splinter party/ies and the year that it/they was/were established.
- **‘Total Number of Terms in Power’**: the number of terms (i.e. the period between two elections) that the party in hand has served in office, be it singlehandedly or as part of a coalition. Users will notice that additional information is provided when they hover over cells that include a red earmark .
- **‘Total Number of Leaderships’**: the number of all leaderships since the party in hand was registered formally as a political party.

Spreadsheet titled *Party Leadership* includes a total of 105 variables which provide users with some basic information about leadership changes in the 18 selected parties/case studies since they were registered formally as political parties. More specifically, this spreadsheet includes 4 variables from *Parties Master*, namely **‘Country’**, **‘Party Name’**, **‘Party Type’** and **‘Total Number of Leaderships’**. Same as above, users can filter data based on **‘Party Type’** by clicking on the arrow next to the variable title. This spreadsheet also includes a number of new variables:

- **‘Party’s 1st Leader’**: the name(s) of the individual(s) or entity that assumed the leadership of the party in hand following its formal registration as a political party. For all ensuing party leaderships, we follow a similar labelling of the respective variables, e.g. **‘Party’s 2nd Leader’**, **‘Party’s 3rd Leader’**, etc.

- ‘1st Leadership Starts’: the date in which the first individual(s) or entity assumed leadership duties in the party in hand following its formal registration. Users will notice that additional information is provided when they hover over cells that include a red earmark . For all ensuing party leadership start dates, we follow a similar labelling of the respective variables, e.g. ‘2nd Leadership Starts’, ‘3rd Leadership Starts’, etc.
- ‘1st Leadership Ends’: the date in which the first leader – individual(s) or entity – of the party in hand surrendered their leadership duties. Users will notice that additional information is provided when they hover over cells that include a red earmark . For all ensuing party leadership end dates, we follow a similar labelling of the respective variables, e.g. ‘2nd Leadership Ends’, ‘3rd Leadership Ends’, etc.
- ‘1st Leadership Days’: the total number of days which the first leader – individual(s) or entity – remained in the leadership of the party in hand. This is calculated by subtracting ‘1st Leadership Starts’ variable from ‘1st Leadership Ends’ variable. Users will notice that additional information is provided when they hover over cells that include a red earmark . For all ensuing total numbers of leadership days, we follow a similar labelling of the respective variables, e.g. ‘2nd Leadership Days’, ‘3rd Leadership Days’, etc. We calculate all ensuing respective variables in the aforementioned way.
- ‘1st Leadership Ends Reason’: this variable briefly describes the reason why the first leader – individual(s) or entity – of the party in hand surrendered their leadership duties. Users will notice that some cells are empty due to a lack of publicly accessible relevant information. Additional information is provided when one hovers over cells that include a red earmark . For all ensuing respective variables, we follow the same labelling format, e.g. ‘2nd Leadership Ends Reason’, ‘3rd Leadership Ends Reason’, etc.
- ‘Leadership Average Days’: the average number of days which an individual(s) or entity remained in the leadership of the party in hand. This is calculated by dividing the sum of all ‘XX Leadership Days’ variables by the ‘Total Number of Leaderships’ variable for the party in hand.

Spreadsheet titled *Parties in Power (since 1990)* includes a total of 142 variables which provide users with some basic information about 10 out of 18 selected parties/case studies that have actively participated in government, be it singlehandedly or as part of a coalition. More specifically, this spreadsheet includes 4 variables from *Parties Master*, namely ‘Country’, ‘Party Name’, ‘Party Type’ and ‘Total Number of Terms in Power’ (NB. Since 1990). Same as previously, the user can filter data based on ‘Party Type’ by clicking on the arrow next to the variable title. This spreadsheet also includes a number of new variables:

- ‘TOTAL NUMBER OF CABINETS’: the number of cabinets to which the party in hand has contributed ministers across all terms it has served in power since 1990.
- ‘(%) TERM 1 EL_P_ST’: the electoral power (%) of the party in hand at the start of its first term in power since 1990. Users will notice that respective election dates are provided when they hover over cells that include a red earmark . For all ensuing respective variables, we follow the same labelling format, e.g. ‘(%) TERM 2 EL_P_ST’, ‘(%) TERM 3 EL_P_ST’, etc.
- ‘Cabinet 1.1 Role’: the position of the party in hand within the first cabinet to which it contributed ministers during its first term in power since 1990. The values range from Junior/Senior Coalition Partner to Single-Party Minority/Majority Government. Users will notice that respective cabinet names are provided when they hover over cells that include a red earmark . For all ensuing respective variables, we follow the same labelling format, e.g. ‘Cabinet 1.2 Role’, ‘Cabinet 1.3 Role’, etc., as well as ‘Cabinet 2.1 Role’, ‘Cabinet 2.2 Role’, etc.

- ‘CAB 1.1 COAL PART’: the initials of the coalition partner(s), if any, in the first cabinet to which the party in hand contributed ministers during its first term in power since 1990. For all ensuing respective variables, we follow the same labelling format, e.g. ‘CAB 1.2 COAL_PART’, ‘CAB 1.3 COAL_PART’, etc., as well as ‘CAB 2.1 COAL_PART’, ‘CAB 2.2 COAL_PART’, etc.
- ‘CAB 1.1 STARTS’: the date in which the first cabinet to which the party in hand contributed ministers during its first term in power since 1990 assumed office duties. For all ensuing respective variables, we follow the same labelling format, e.g. ‘CAB 1.2 STARTS’, ‘CAB 1.3 STARTS’, etc., as well as ‘CAB 2.1 STARTS’, ‘CAB 2.2 STARTS’, etc.
- ‘CAB 1.1 ENDS’: the date in which the first cabinet to which the party in hand contributed ministers during its first term in power since 1990 surrendered office duties. For all ensuing respective variables, we follow the same labelling format, e.g. ‘CAB 1.2 ENDS’, ‘CAB 1.3 ENDS’, etc., as well as ‘CAB 2.1 ENDS’, ‘CAB 2.2 ENDS’, etc.
- ‘CAB 1.1 DAYS’: the total number of days which the first cabinet to which the party in hand contributed ministers during its first term in power since 1990 remained in office. This is calculated by subtracting ‘CAB 1.1 STARTS’ variable from ‘CAB 1.1 ENDS’ variable. For all ensuing total numbers of days in office, we follow the same labelling format, e.g. ‘CAB 1.2 DAYS’, ‘CAB 1.3 DAYS’, etc., as well as ‘CAB 2.1 DAYS’, ‘CAB 2.2 DAYS’, etc.
- ‘CAB 1.1 END REASON’: this variable briefly describes the reason why the first cabinet to which the party in hand contributed ministers during its first term in power since 1990 ended. For all ensuing respective variables, we follow the same labelling format, e.g. ‘CAB 1.2 END REASON’, ‘CAB 1.3 END REASON’, etc., as well as ‘CAB 2.1 END REASON’, ‘CAB 2.2 END REASON’, etc.
- ‘CAB 1.1 MIN. POSTS SHARE’: the ministerial posts share of the party in hand upon appointment of the first cabinet to which it contributed ministers during its first term in power since 1990. For all ensuing respective variables, we follow the same labelling format, e.g. ‘CAB 1.2 MIN. POSTS SHARE’, ‘CAB 1.3 MIN. POSTS SHARE’, etc., as well as ‘CAB 2.1 MIN. POSTS SHARE’, ‘CAB 2.2 MIN. POSTS SHARE’, etc.
- ‘CAB 1.1 MIN. POSTS TITLE’: the title(s) of the ministerial post(s) which the party in hand received upon appointment of the first cabinet to which it contributed ministers during its first term in power since 1990. For all ensuing respective variables, we follow the same labelling format, e.g. ‘CAB 1.2 MIN. POSTS TITLE’, ‘CAB 1.3 MIN. POSTS TITLE’, etc., as well as ‘CAB 2.1 MIN. POSTS TITLE’, ‘CAB 2.2 MIN. POSTS TITLE’, etc.
- ‘(%) TERM 1 EL P END’: the electoral power (%) of the party in hand at the end of its first term in power since 1990. Users will notice that respective election dates are provided when they hover over cells that include a red earmark . For all ensuing respective variables, we follow the same labelling format, e.g. ‘(%) TERM 2 EL_P_END’, ‘(%) TERM 3 EL_P_END’, etc.
- ‘CABINET AVERAGE DAYS’: the average number of days which the party in hand has remained in power since 1990. This is calculated by dividing the sum of all ‘CAB X.X DAYS’ variables by the ‘TOTAL NUMBER OF CABINETS’ variable for the party in hand.

Finally, *all remaining spreadsheets* include tables and graphs based on the electoral results of the 18 selected parties/case studies, as well as of all significant parties that have participated in elections in the respective countries since 1990.